

PEDAGOGICAL-PSYCHOLOGICAL FEATURES OF THE FORMATION OF SOCIAL CONSCIOUSNESS IN PRESCHOOL-ADULT CHILDREN

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6628452>

Annotation. In this article, the pedagogical and psychological features of the formation of social consciousness in preschool-adult children are analyzed, in which the ways of formation of social consciousness in preschool age, determining factors are studied. It is also based on the study of the impact of social consciousness development.

Keywords: preschool education, organization of preschool education, older children, social consciousness, formation of social consciousness, social competence, the concept of "I", developing child, self-assessment, social cognition.

Today, upbringing children of preschool age in the Republic in the spirit of perfection of their high spiritual qualities, improvement of national spirituality, rich cultural heritage, respect for historical traditions, universal values, love for motherland, loyalty to the ideas of independence are the decisive factor of all reforms carried out in our country.

In the curriculum "the first step", developed on the basis of "state requirements for the development of children of primary and preschool age", social compensation is introduced as one of the General important compensations for a child of preschool age (6-7 years). Social competence is the ability to behave in a way that is consistent with the rules and norms of morality in communication with adults and peers in life situations, after the completion of educational and educational activities in the field of "socio-emotional development", the child 6-7 years: will have an idea of his "I" and the role of other people in the; communicates with adults and peers in accordance with the situation; finds ways out constructively from complex situations[1].

Interpersonal knowledge has evolved throughout human life. This is primarily due to the development of human intellectual and personal spheres. The way a person shapes his Self depends on how he understands and builds the world around him and his relationships with

people. There are two directions in the development of social cognition: in the way of knowing oneself as a social object or as a social subject.

In adults, both are manifested in direction. It is difficult to pinpoint the direction of social cognition in childhood.

We observe the sources of the formation of social consciousness in the preschool age from the earliest age. N.A. Menchinskaya, for example, expresses the mastery of the material of the concepts of child development diaries, and gives an example of the child's understanding of the general meaning of words, which means the people around the child - mother and father. In the second year of life, children may be distracted from their father's individual imagination and may realize that they may be "foreign" fathers [3; 392-b.]. This example illustrates that a child at an early age can understand social information. It can generalize social concepts within certain limits. At an early age, a child's social consciousness is mainly focused on understanding the social nature of the people around him - mother and father, sisters and brothers, grandparents and great-grandparents.

The dynamics of the formation of the child's cognitive activity is crucial for the development of social cognition in preschool children.

An important aspect of a preschooler's cognitive development is memory. With the increase in physiological capacity, mnemonic abilities are also formed in the preschool child, and memory becomes the center of consciousness.

An important aspect of cognitive development is children's thinking and speech. In preschool, there is an active formation of concepts, including social objects: the concept of self and other people. The development of speech and thinking helps to increase the child's knowledge and imagination on issues related to the world around him.

The question of how preschoolers acquire differentiated social knowledge about themselves and other people, how they feel about themselves, their peers and different attitudes towards adults, is the key to forming a holistic self-image. It encourages thinking.

According to SI Rozum, the image of "I" is a central mental phenomenon that should be considered "as a product of communication." In this sense, the image of "I" is consistent with the "I-concept" of man. In general, the image of "I" is formed by the child's acceptance of the role of

adults, that is, the social environment. The image of "I" is a complex structural product, which includes an element of self-control, self-assessment, positioning in the social situation, the main function of which is the process of social cognition of the universe. The construction of appropriate expression is to ensure the internal conformity of the individual, the relative stability of his behavior. The development of the individual, his activities and behavior are significantly influenced by the self-concept.

Adults play a variety of social roles, such as father, mother, and abstract adult, and have a certain influence on the nature of the preschooler's social interactions and, consequently, on later adolescence.

According to S.I. Rozum, one of the consequences of the important fundamental psychological impact of adult influence is the formation of social consciousness in the child - subjective sociality, a sense of belonging to the social world, a sense of "we" [5; 271-b.]. In this context, G. Craig believes that adults can help children in two ways. First, provide examples and explanations for teaching social skills. Second, to create an environment in which children can have a successful experience of interacting with their peers in a fully communicative process [6; 428-b.].

Building your own Self is directly related to the culture, traditions, and customs that the child is growing and developing. The role of adults in relation to the child plays a special role. Therefore, according to O. Conner, acceptance and love lead to the formation of a sense of security and the normal development of the individual. Explicit denial leads to aggression, criminal behavior, and emotional distress. Excessive demands create frustration and insecurity. Excessive care, especially in social relationships, leads to infantilism, the inability to act independently. As a result, the child acquires certain personality traits that are clearly visible to others and often invisible to him.

The imbalance between the self-real, the self-ideal, and the self-reflection can lead to a distortion of the self-concept as a holistic structural individual product.

Hence, the process of development of human social consciousness continues throughout his life. The construction of self-image is connected with the culture and traditions of human development. The conceptual basis of self-knowledge is formed in preschool and is strengthened in the child's self-image, which in turn determines the dynamics of his self-concept.

The position of adults in relation to the school-age child requires a balance of the structural components of their I-concepts. The most important mechanisms of formation of social consciousness also have their roots in childhood, the development of which is associated with the formation of cognitive and personal spheres of man. If the adults take into account the potential of the child, the dynamics of mental mechanisms and the results of the development of social cognition, provide the conditions for the formation of the growing child's self-concept, the child's mental world will be richer.

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